

Secular parallels to the eschatological discourse in the Latvian periodicals in the Russian language (1920s – 1930s)

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Introduction I

The eschatological trends in the European intellectual discourse during the *fin de siècle* resulted in the large spectrum of eschatological (or apocalyptic) ideas after the "Great War". "The Decline of the West" (1918) by Oswald Spengler, "Das Spektrum Europas" (1928) by Graf Hermann Keyserling reflected the concept of a fall of Western civilization / fall of Europe on the eve of rivalry with the "new" folks. Attempts to seeking for new renaissance were based both on the religious interpretation of the spiritual rebirth and on the secularized concept of the "soul" considered as "soul of the folk" or "soul of the culture". *Spiritualization of the culture* as the repercussions of the "Enlightenment project" in the first line, as well as the reaction to the post-war intellectual and axiological distraction is observed also in Latvian intellectual context of the 1st part of 20th century. Moreover, the different ethnic communities constituted the Latvian society in this period contributed different concepts both on the level of the academic discourse and of the public discourse in media (periodicals). Suggested paper will be focused on the media discourse in Russian reflected differences among the diverse Russian community, Russian émigré, and other groups used Russian language in public communication. Two significant almanacs in Russian language – *Perezvony* (Chimes) and *Rodnaya Starina* (Native Antiquity) – aimed to provide the concept about the "lost past" maintaining and partly constructing the mythologeme of *Holy Rus'* through the glimpse of literature, art, and music.

The Russian minority in Latvia: between diaspora and community

Linguistic and cultural identity were quite important factors that allowed Russians in Latvia to recognize themselves as a "national minority" during the 1920s in the new socio-political situation. However, a common language did not yet mean a commonality of political views and interests, or even a commonality of cultural memory.

Despite the fact that throughout the interwar period, active public figures, publicists and politicians from the Russian environment appealed to the sense of unity of the Russian people, pointing to belonging to a single "community", in general, the process of forming the self-awareness of Latvian Russians as a national minority during this period remained unfinished. The reasons for this were significant differences in the cultural experience of the Russian population.

Conventionally, three main groups of Latvian Russians can be distinguished:

- 1) Russian Old Believers, who historically lived compactly in large cities of Latgale - Dvinsk (Daugavpils) and Rezhitsa (Rēzekne), on the territory of Eastern Latvia in the villages of Dvinsk, Rezhitsa and Lucin districts (now Daugavpils, Rēzekne and Ludza regions), as well as in Jakobstadt (Jēkabpils) and Rīga. Already at the end of the 1660s the first communities of Old Believers appeared on the territory of Latgale (to that time, a part of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth).¹ That fact in the eyes of the Old Believers themselves is indisputable evidence of their strong connection with this region. The Riga Grebenshchikov community, founded in 1760, is today one of the largest non-priest communities outside of Russia;
- 2) Russians who belonged to Orthodox and *Edinoverie* parishes, living both in the villages of Latgale and in large cities throughout Latvia even before the start of the First World War. The number of Orthodox Russians gradually increased throughout the 18th – 19th centuries, including as a result of changes in the official government policy in the North-Western region of the Russian empire in the 2nd half of the 19th century: already in the 1830s–40s, after the first Polish uprising (1831), measures to strengthen “Orthodoxy and the Russian element” were provided. As a result, Russian peasants were resettled to free state-owned lands (some of whom were Old Believers); during the uprising of 1863, the Old Believers opposed the Polish landowners, which contributed to the suppression of the uprising. On the lands located on the border with the Kingdom of Poland that remained free after the expulsion of the Polish landowners the government gave permission to the Old Believers to settle, providing them with various benefits.²
 In the late 19th century, the Russian ethnic group included 154,563 people (8% of the total population of present-day territory of Latvia, i.e. Courland, Livonia and part of the Vitebsk province (Dvinsk, Rezhitsa and Lyutsin districts)), Orthodox and *edinovercy* accounted for 79,928 people or 51.7% Russians, Old Believers - 65,521 (42.3%), 6% Russians represented other religions; in 1930, out of 201,778 Russians (10.62% of the inhabitants of Latvia), 104,791 (51.93%) considered themselves Orthodox, 91,092 (45.15%) considered themselves Old Believers.³
- 3) In the period 1919 – 1921, the so-called “white emigrants” are a rather heterogeneous group both in terms of ethnic composition (however, classifying oneself as “Russian” in the period under review, in general, was not an indication of ethnic origin, but rather of the Orthodox religion, connection with

¹ Brief insight in the history of Old Believers in Latvia see: Подмазов А. Староверие в Латвии // Барановский В., Поташенко Г. Староверие Балтии и Польши. Краткий исторический и библиографический словарь. Вильнюс: Aidai, 2005. С. 359–364.

² Attempt to describe the resettlement process from the perspective of the Old Believers: Кирничанская И. Исследование истории возникновения поселения и общины староверов в Данишевке в XVII – XIX веках. Дипломная работа. Рига: Гребенщиковское духовное училище, 2013. URL: <https://www.russkije.lv/ru/pub/read/Kirnichanskaya/Kirnichanskaya-1.html> (30.10.2019).

³ Trešā tautas skaitīšana Latvijā 1930. gadā. M. Skujenieka teksts un redakcija. Rīga: Valsts Statistiskā pārvalde, 1930. 171. lpp.

Russian culture and Russia), and by religious affiliation and ideological positions. Rīga, Liepāja, Daugavpils and Rēzekne were the cities in which Russian emigrants settled most willingly.

The first two categories are usually classified as "local Russians", while emigrants from Soviet Russia who found shelter on the territory of Latvia partly organically entered into the environment of "local" Russians, having close relatives here. But a significant part of the emigrants preferred to remain isolated, maintaining contacts with the "Russian émigré" in other countries of Europe rather than with the local Russian community. The Latvian historian Tatyana Feigmane points to such a demarcation in her monograph on Russians in pre-war Latvia.⁴

However, as an exception, the opposite trend can be noted. In the 1920s, a circle of well-educated Russian youth formed in Latvia, with experience of social work in large centers of the Russian émigré, in particular in Prague, which was considered at that time the "Russian Oxford". Among the graduates of the Russian Faculty of Law at Prague Charles University was Ivan Zavoloko (*Иван Никифорович Заволоко*, 1897–1984), who came from a hereditary family of Latgalian Old Believers. Zavoloko's personal contacts allowed him to organize meetings between members of the circle of young Old Believers (Zealots of Russian Antiquity / *Ревнителы русской старины*) he led and prominent representatives of the Russian emigration who visited Riga. Among the guests were representatives of the French society "Icon", with whom I.N. Zavoloko corresponded as editor of the almanac "Native Antiquity" (*Родная Страница*, 1927 – 1933). Visit of P.P. Muratov to Riga in the late 1920s served as an incentive for the professional study and restoration of icons of the Assumption Prayer house of the Grebenshchikov community.

The Russian-reading audience in Latvia (1920s-1930s)

The interwar period, in the context of the cultural history of the Russian minority in Latvia, reflects the experience of forming and partly constructing the cultural memory of the community of Russians who found themselves outside of Russia. For one part of this community it opened the new opportunities and significantly improved the legal situation (the case of the Orthodox Old believers, at the same time, the majority of this community was not able to appreciate it practically due of their political *alienation* from the state institutions). The other part of Russian community rather lost its comfortable feeling of stability in unshakeable faith of empire power. There are also a democratic wing that were clearly aware of the way to the independence of Latvia.

During the parliamentary period of the Republic of Latvia, before the coup d'etat of Kārlis Ulmanis on May 15–16, 1934, Riga and Latvia (especially Latgale) in view of Russian émigré retained the unofficial status of the space of "Russian diaspora" ("*Baltische Randstaaten*", thanks to a fairly large "local" Russian population, perceived

⁴ Фейгмане Т. Русские в довоенной Латвии. На пути к интеграции. Рига: Балтийский русский институт, 2000.

as the space of existence of the former, pre-revolutionary Russia). However, the composition of this population was far from homogeneous. By the beginning of the 1920s, Latvian Russians represented a rather specific group, that consolidated mainly on the base of using Russian language as the main language of communication in the family and in public space, language of education and the common memory of the historical - but lost the features of a really existing state - homeland.

One of specific features of the reading audience that consumed the media content in Russian language in the interwar period in Latvia was its ethnic, political, religious and even linguistic heterogeneity. Among the newspaper and magazine readers were not only Russians (*local* and Russian émigré), but also Jews, Poles, Germans and other ethnic groups who used Russian language in the communication. On the one hand, it should be noted the historical coexistence of all three most common languages in the field of professional culture and public media since the late 19th century (Latvian, German, Russian). On the other hand, the positive facet of multilingual situation should be critically balanced: the politic of Russification implemented during the Alexander III and partly Nikolai II affected the educational practices and intellectual discourse, where Russian language consistently competed with German. In any case, the reading audience of the Russian periodicals could not be limited to just one ethnic group. So, also the expectations of the audience were rather controversial than similar.

The periodical in Russian language were aimed at the wide political spectrum, articulated reflections more on the political and economic situation, on the actual cultural events, and less on the deeper philosophic reflection regarding the historical process or cultural changes. Nevertheless even the needs of *self-reformulation* (or, more precisely *we-reformulation*) in context of adaptation to the status of national (ethnic) minorities, establishing of the new kind of linguistic and cultural communities, that should find compromise with the leading Latvian society, but simultaneously to safe their specific identity, to be integrated and solidary, but not assimilated and discriminated.⁵

Among each of both large linguistic communities – Russian and German – were different groups of political, economic interests, as well as different educational level and cultural experience. The topic of the eschatological discourse and its secular parallels resonated therefore more educated readers who were familiar with the philosophy and literature; moreover, they should have experience of the intellectual reflections. The Latvian researcher of the Russian press, Yury Abyzov, described “*Segodnya*”, the most popular newspaper in Russian language in the interwar period, as the newspaper that was “not ‘émigré’, or ‘anti-bolshevist’, or ‘jewish’”. It was considered itself Latvian, in as much as it catered for the multi-ethnic society of the

⁵ More about the establishing of minorities policy and identity see: Hanovs, D. & Volkovs, V. (2020) Types of Social Memory and the Subordination of Identities of Ethnic Minorities in Latvia. In: *Europe thirty years after 1989. Transformations of values, memory, and identity*. Kavaliauska, T. (ed.). Leiden: Koninklijke Brill NV, p. 105–128 (Value inquiry book series; vol. 359).

republic, which had grown in an atmosphere of Russian culture", in addition to Russians there were also Latvians, Germans, Poles, and Jews".⁶

Regarding specific of Russian-reading audience could be pointed out the Old Believers' group that like the other community of *local* Russians (who lived on territory of Latvia before the proclamation of the independent Latvian state in 1918) represents both groups, the rural and urban population, moreover, the majority of Old Believers belonged to the peasants. However the literacy rate among the Orthodox Old Believers was higher than among other Orthodox peasants, the reading repertoire in this religious community mostly was connected with different kinds of religious literature (hagiography, Psalter, handwritten collections of significant quotes from the writings of Church fathers etc.). The cultural practice to read secular literature or periodicals only gradually appeared while the trust to the "non-religious" utilitarian books established as a consequence of educational practice.⁷ This slow transition to the new cultural practices on the countryside partly was a reason of the low interest in art magazines and almanacs among the Russian rural inhabitants. If the newspaper were seen as "practical" reading that could be helpful in everyday life, then almanacs were perceived rather as expensive entertainment. This kind of reading wasn't welcomed among the Old Believers who practiced reading mostly as a part of religious ritual. Thus, during the period of 1920s and 1930s gradually the new readings customs aimed to the broadening intellectual horizon were developed among the rural Old Believers, provided by journals and text collections published by Old Believers intellectuals (for example, journal *Rodnaya Starina*).

The periodicals in Russian language in Latvia (1920s-1930s)

The most popular newspaper in Russian language was the *Segodnya* ('Today'), which was issued between 1919 and 1940.⁸ From 1924 an evening edition, *Segodnya Večerom*, was published. The newspaper was widely known in the Russian emigrant milieu outside Latvia. Material was sent to the newspaper from famous Russian writers

⁶ Абызов, Юрий. 20 лет русской печати в независимой Латвии // Русские в Латвии. История и современность. Выпуск 2. Рига, 1997. <http://www.russkije.lv/ru/pub/read/rus-in-latvia-edition2/abizov-rus-latvii-2.html>

⁷ More about the historical and cultural context of reading practices in the late 19th century in Russian empire see: Reitblat, Abram. The Book and the Peasant in the Nineteenth and the Beginning of the Twentieth Century: From Illiteracy to the Religious Book to the Secular Book. In: *Reading Russia, Vol. 2*, édité par Damiano Rebecchini et Raffaella Vassena, Ledizioni, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.4000/books.ledizioni.13174>. <https://books.openedition.org/ledizioni/13174>

⁸ More about the historical context and publishing policy: Л. Флейшман, Русская газета «Сегодня» и культура русского зарубежья 1930-х годов, в: Л. Флейшман, Ю. Абызов, Б. Равдин, Русская печать в Риге: из истории газеты «Сегодня» 1930-х годов: На грани эпох, Stanford 1997, кн. I, с. 49-51; general information about *Segodnya* ibid. 155-157.

Bibliographic description: Газета *Сегодня* 1919-1940. Роспись. Часть 1. - 1918-1930; Часть 2. - 1931-1940. Составил Ю.Абызов. - Рига: Латвийская Национальная библиотека, 2001.

and poets – Arkady Averchenko, Konstantin Balmont, Ivan Bunin, Alexander Kuprin, Nadezhda Taffy and Ivan Shmelev.

At the end of 1924 the first edition of the *Slovo* (Слово, 'The Word', 1925 – 1929, № 1–1035) newspaper was issued, of which the publisher was the insurance company "Salamandra" headed by Nikolay Belotsvetov (Николай Алексеевич Белоцветов, 1863 – 1935). However, the paper could not create any competition for *Segodnya* as it catered exclusively for the right-wing Russian reader. In 1929 the paper ceased publication.

Such was also the fate of other publications of "Salamandra", amongst which the most significant was the weekly art and literature magazine *Perezvony* (Перезвоны, 'Chimes', 1925 – 1929, nr.1 – 14, editor Sergey Belotsvetov, brother of Nikolay Belotsvetov (Сергей Алексеевич Белоцветов, 1873 - 1938), literary section editor Boris Zaytsev (Борис Константинович Зайцев, 1881 – 1972)). The cover design for this magazine created Mstislav Dobužinsky, among the main authors were Nikolai Berežansky, Ivan Lukaš, Nadežda Teffi etc.

With support of "Salamandra" and Nikolay Belotsvetov were published also magazine for youth *Yuny chitatel'* (Юный читатель, 'Young Reader', 1925 – 1926, nr. 1- 24) collections dedicated to the Day of Russian Culture, Russian classic literature.

The almanac "*Rodnaya Starina*" (Родная Старина, *Native Antiquity*, 1927 – 1933, nr. 1- 13, editor and publisher Ivan Zavoloko). Members of the editorial board: I. N. Zavoloko, Daniil Mikhailov, A. K. Fomichev. Magazine was excellent illustrated (design of this magazine used graphic works by D. Stelletsy and I. Bilibin), and contained a large spectrum of articles on the history of Old Believers, history of Vygoretsia, icon painting, ancient Russian architecture, church singing, history and contemporary situation in Old Believer communities in the Baltic States etc. Zavoloko himself not only edited the magazine, but was also the author of most articles, signed by first and last name or pseudonyms. In the edition of *Native Antiquity*, Zavoloko focused on magazine *Perezvony*, but the main aim of the almanac was religious education. "Our main task is to awaken religious self-awareness in young people, to arouse interest in their antiquity, in their identity", with this words opened the first preliminary issue of the almanac in November 1927. However the content of the journal reflected not only religious issues, but also literature (novels, poetry) and art that in secular order interpreted ideas of Christian spirituality. Every issue was dedicated to a specific topic and illustrated with reproductions of paintings by famous Russian artists (N.K. Roerich - *Human Affairs* (Nr. 1), *St. Sergius* (Nr. 4), *Solovetsky Monastery* (Nr. 4), M. V. Nesterov - *Silence* (Nr. 4), *On the Volga* (Nr. 3), *Holy Rus'* (Nr. 11-12), V. I. Surikov - *Boyarinia Morozova* (Nr. 3), A. M. Vasnetsov - *Ancient Monastery* (Nr. 4); Sandro Botticelli – *Madonna* (Nr.5 - 6).

In general, over 70 newspapers and 80 magazines in Russian were published at different times in independent Latvia in the 1920s and 1930s.⁹ After the authoritarian regime came to power in 1934 journalists found themselves under press censorship. In 1940, after the USSR occupied Latvia, all former Russian newspapers in Latvia irrespectively of their political propensity were closed down, and many journalists suffered repression.¹⁰

Case study I. Ideas of (*secular*) eschatology in periodical almanac *Rodnaya Starina*

The concept of "antiquity" (*старина*) in Old Believers discursive practices is etymologically connected with the emphasis on longevity and continuity of tradition (compare: Old Belief < *old faith*; Old Orthodoxy, *Древлеправославие*). The content of this concept was formed mainly in the Orthodox theological discourse of the 16th – 17th centuries and reflects the process of conceptualization of a special version of Russian Orthodoxy. The strengthening of autocephaly of the Russian Orthodox Church took place in a complex cultural confrontation with the Greek Orthodox tradition. From this point of view, the mid-17th century schism in the Russian Orthodox Church can be seen not only as an internal church conflict, but also as a deeper cultural conflict caused by different cultural ideals.

The understanding of *antiquity* in the context of religious practice and everyday culture is associated with the main range of issues in the debate around the reforms carried out in the Russian Church in the middle of the 17th century. The criterion of antiquity was also one of the main arguments of Patriarch Nikon, who sought to return to the "ancient" Greek model of church ritual.

The question of following the *principles of antiquity* (*заветы старины*) was one of the main ones in the polemics between opponents of the reforms and the "Nikonians": the main objection of supporters of the *Old Faith* was associated with the obvious contradiction of the reforms carried out by Nikon with the authority of the Russian church tradition. The desire to restore the Russian ideal of piety in the middle of the 17th century was a response to troubled times that brought destabilization in the spheres of both political and religious life. Shifting the sacral meaning from the universal supra-national Orthodox tradition and theology to the specially regional Russian Orthodox *spirituality*, emphasizing contribution of Russian Saints (systematization of hagiographic texts) was an inseparable part in the historical process of establishing autocephaly Russian Orthodox Church since the Council of a Hundred Chapters (*Стоглавый собор*, Moscow, 1551). Since this period the eschatological

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¹⁰ Russian press of interwar Latvia. <http://www.russkije.lv/en/lib/read/press-in-pre-war-latvia.html>

concept of *Moscow - Third Rome* gained not only its political dimension, but also cultural facet. The special *Russian-ness*, articulated in the Orthodox tradition as *holiness / sanctity (святость)* gradually influenced the secular literature, art, music that established the field of the cultural texts in sense of European Enlightenment.

The marked interpretation of *Old faith* as a manifestation of the "specific nation" religious spirit could be identified also in the 1920s in the works of Russian philosophers and historians who continued their intellectual activities in emigration. For example, Georgy Fedotov (*Георгий Петрович Федотов* (1886 – 1951) who in 1912-1913 has served his shorted extradition in Melluži (Karlsbad) near Rīga due of his repeated activities in the Social Democratic Party. In late 1917 he organized together with the Alexander Meier (*Александр Александрович Мейер*, 1874 – 1939) the circle with symbolical name of "Resurrection" (*Воскресение*, Petrograd / Leningrad, 1917 – 1928) as continuation of the ideas of the Sankt-Petersburg Religious Philosophical Society (Санкт-Петербургское религиозно-философское общество, 1907 – 1917¹¹), represented the intellectual discussions in his edited journal "The Free Voices" (*Свободные голоса*, 2 issues, 1918). Joining this circle marked for him the beginning of a religious search (the result of which was his return to the Orthodoxy), and in scientific work led to a gradual reorientation of his interests from the history of the European Middle Ages to the history of Rus' and Russia. He emigrated in 1925, was involved into various religious and religious-philosophical circles and associations. While living in France, he met N.A. Berdyaev, gets closer to I.I. Fondaminsky (Bunakov) and E.Yu. Skobtsova (Mother Maria). Since 1927 he participated in the activities of the Russian Student Christian Movement (РСХД, founded in 1923) and the Orthodox Cause (*Православное Дело*) association. In the 1930s, Fedotov. actively participated in the ecumenical movement to bring the Orthodox and Anglican churches closer together; in 1931–1939 together with I.I. Fondaminsky and F.A. Stepun publishes the Christian Democratic magazine "Novy Grad", "Krug"(published by N. Berdyaev).¹²

Addressing the theme of *Old faith* and *antiquity* in the almanac's articles was attempt to justify or explain in philosophical perspective the tensions and conflicts in the history of Russia. The Orthodox Church's Schism in this sense just ranked in the chain of past and subsequent conflicts, with their causes linked to the contradictions inherent in Russian culture "organically." The idea about the heterogeneous nature of Russian cultural *spiritual* heritage articulated by Russian religious thinkers at the beginning of the 20th century shifted on a different level. This "spiritual heterogeneity" of Russian culture was interpreted as a main factor of the *otherness* of the the Russian religious and cultural experience.

Thus, the new trend in the interpretation and perception of the *Old faith* can be found: from a religious point of view, there is no need to look for a positive role of the Old Believers religious tradition, but the customs of the Old Believers, especially the forms of everyday culture are interpreted as close as possible to the "authentic"

¹¹ Религиозно-философское общество в Санкт-Петербурге (Петрограде): История в материалах и документах: 1907—1917: В 3 т. / Сост., подгот. текста, вступ. ст. и примеч. О. Т. Ермишина, О. А. Коростелева, Л. В. Хачатурян и др

¹² Fedotov G. A Treasury of Russian Spirituality. New York, Sheed & Ward, 1948.

core of Russian life. So, the Old Believers' tradition gain positive appreciation rather as a cultural phenomenon than as a specific religious practice and heritage. This paradoxical (and not necessarily clearly articulated) theological "neutralisation" of *Old faith* including this tradition not in continuum of the religious, but of the cultural phenomena is remarkable trend in the context of the discussion on the "special path" of Russia and *spiritualization* of Russian culture.

Conclusions

Antiquity as a heritage of *Russian holiness*, as a criterion of the truth of faith (to live according to the "*testaments of our ancestors*") remains the central motive for discussions among both Old Believers and Russian Orthodox. In the 1st half of the 20th century, especially after the manifesto of 1905 in Russian empire, and throughout the interwar period in Latvia, collecting antiquities became the main value vector of the activities of Old Believers and Old Believers' public organizations, aimed at preserving tradition and its continuation in the experience of the younger generation. The printed media of Old Believers (almanac, collections of articles) represented these attempts not only for the Old Believers' readers, but also for larger audience. These issues still are the sources for research of intellectual history of Old Believers and local Russian community.

The activity of groups and associations of Latvian Old Believers in the interwar period shows the efforts to restore the "ethnographic" side of the *Old Faith*, by paying attention to the peculiarities of household arrangements and ancient Russian dress, the ancient manner of singing and forms of church art, to look for a way for the younger generation of Old Believers to be able to internalize the "*principles of the ancestors*", which gradually disappeared from the cultural practices of the Old Believers. The discourse about *antiquity* as about the only one possible form of existence in a "fallen world" constructs a secular eschatological model of the *end of culture* and escaping into *world of antiquity*.